

Exploring Pedagogical Frontiers: Narratives of Elementary English Educators

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Abstract. English teachers develop students' language proficiency, critical thinking, and appreciation for literature despite their challenges in this endeavor. This study explored the lived experiences of English teachers in public elementary schools in Tugbok A District, Division of Davao City. Using purposive sampling, this phenomenological research study looked at the challenges, coping strategies, and educational insights of 10 different English teachers in the said district schools. Creswell's Thematic Analysis was used to generate themes from the experiences of English Teachers. The findings revealed the experiences of English teachers in public elementary schools. Three themes emerge: the scarcity of diverse English teaching materials, students' lack of motivation and interest, and low literacy among students. The coping mechanisms of English teachers in public elementary schools and the emergence of three themes: professional development and language-focused activities. Somehow, teachers know how to handle the students' concerns about English teaching materials, lack of motivation and interest, and low literacy among students. The educational insights of English Teachers in Public Elementary Schools. The emerging of the four themes. The technology used was crucial in English classrooms; contextualized learning and support are needed to foster it. In addition, English teachers believe that contextualization, support, fostering student relationships, and technology are important in an English Classroom.

KEY WORDS

1. English teachers
2. public elementary schools
3. experiences
4. coping strategies
5. narratives

Date Received: May 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: June 01, 2024 — Date Published: July 1, 2024

1. Introduction

English teachers play an essential role in shaping the foundational language skills of the students as well as fostering a love for literature at a crucial stage in their development. Understanding their experiences, challenges, and innovative pedagogical strategies can provide invaluable insights into effective teaching practices and curriculum development. This study is especially significant in addressing the varied needs of students in a classroom setting that is becoming more multicultural and technologically sophisticated. Policymakers and

educational leaders can improve teacher support, improve student outcomes, and ultimately advance language education by learning from the experiences and viewpoints of elementary English educators. Relatively, the English language is taught at almost all schools in different parts and regions of the world. It has consistently proven its value in the realm of education. Since immemorial, it has empowered students to articulate their thoughts in a universal medium, enabling effective communication with individuals of various linguistic backgrounds. The English language also serves as a

conduit for everyday interactions and facilitates the process of knowledge acquisition. English educators are significant in the early stages of a child's primary school education. However, as it must be acknowledged that mastering this intricate language is essential, its complexity varies for everyone. Diverse factors influence the students' English proficiency, highlighting the complicated nature of language acquisition. With students struggling to learn the language, various classroom studies and statistical data reinforce and support it. Language is a primary means of communication, enabling people to share thoughts and ideas. The world is home to many languages, with each country having national and local languages spoken in different areas. Some languages are widely spoken, while fewer people know others. In today's globalized world, the importance of English cannot be overlooked. It is a common language spoken in many places. English is widely used, not only in countries like the US and the UK but also by many people in other countries. About a billion people worldwide speak English, including those who use it as a second language. Furthermore, English is the official language in 67 countries and a secondary official language in 27 more. This shows English's widespread influence on communication and international relations (Ilyosovna, 2020). In the international arena, Education First's English Proficiency Index (2020) reveals that over 20 Asian countries lag behind ten other countries regarding language proficiency. Some notable countries include Thailand, Indonesia, Vietnam, and Myanmar. The international index also unveils that Asia generally declined slightly in its performance from its preceding years, with almost half the countries surveyed registering a drop in score. Nonetheless, it has always been manifested that many countries around the globe that scored low to very low English proficiency outnumber those with high to very high proficiency levels (Ang et al., 2021). In another study con-

ducted by Listyariyani (2018) in Jembrana Regency about the Teachers' Perceptions of Teaching English for Young Learners (TEYL), they identified challenges including limited use of diverse media, insufficient preparation time, and a lack of formal training in English language teaching. Interviews and observations also show that, even though teachers acknowledge the significance of different TEYL components, their ability to apply these strategies successfully is severely hampered by resource and practical limitations. The study emphasizes the need for increased support and resources to close the gap between teachers' perceptions and classroom practices, thereby improving the efficacy of English language education for young learners. Another study by Khulel (2021) explored the challenges English teachers face in rural areas when teaching English to young learners based on data collected from interviews. Teachers reported that students' socio-economic status significantly impacts their motivation and success in learning English, as parents frequently prioritize work over their children's education. Furthermore, English's status as a local content subject rather than a core subject results in insufficient instructional time and resources, which impedes effective teaching. The pandemic exacerbated these issues by complicating lesson delivery, particularly given the challenges of online education and teachers' lack of digital skills. Overall, the study emphasizes the need for increased support and resources to address the multifaceted challenges of rural English language education. In the same report, the Philippines slipped four notches to 22nd out of 111 countries with an EPI score of 278. Though it is still categorized as "high proficiency," the country has kept slipping away from its 13th spot in 2016, 15th in 2017, 14th in 2018, and 20th in 2019 (Banzuelo, 2022). Moreover, the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) research tested around 600,000 students aged 15 in 79 participating countries. The study

found that the Philippines ranked the lowest in Reading Comprehension with 340, one of the basic macro-skills one must master, the lowest score in all countries surveyed. This bears the notion that the current state of English language skills among students in the nation is concerning. Numerous factors may contribute to this situation, including insufficient resources, overcrowded classrooms, a shortage of educational materials, and, most of all, the teachers' pedagogical approaches and methods of instruction. The state of English language education in the country falls short of the required standards in the domains of reading, listening, writing, and speaking, which means there is a need to unlock the underlying issues faced by English language teachers, especially in the primary or elementary level where English language learning is deemed crucial (Romero Papango, 2020). In Region XI, particularly in Tugbok A District, Davao City, many English language teachers in the local public elementary schools have also noticed the concerning reality of this issue. Students encounter difficulties in their English sub-

ject areas as teachers grapple to bridge differing problems. In this milieu, this study explored the challenges English language teachers face in public elementary schools across Tugbok A District, Division of Davao City. Previous research has focused alone on the challenges of English language teachers and students within a single elementary school from another separately. Hence, this study endeavored to uncover broader issues English language teachers face in district-wide public elementary schools, contributing to a more comprehensive analysis of this phenomenon.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to investigate the experiences of English language teachers in public elementary schools in Tugbok A District, Division of Davao City. This study intended to capture insights from the challenges, coping mechanisms, and educational insights of teachers from different schools within the district.

1.2. Research Questions—Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of English language teachers in teaching in public elementary schools?
- (2) What coping mechanisms are employed by English language teachers in teaching public elementary schools?
- (3) What educational insights did English language teachers learn from their experiences teaching public elementary schools?

1.3. Definition of Terms—Accordingly, this research study recognized English language teachers' challenges in public elementary schools. Hence, the study was deemed beneficial for the following: Department of Education Officials. The findings of this study would contribute valuable insights by highlighting the specific challenges faced by English language teachers in public elementary schools. By identifying these challenges, educational policymakers and administrators could develop targeted strategies and interventions to enhance

the quality of English language instruction and overall classroom dynamics in an enormous scope. School Heads. This research would supply pertinent information and trustworthy data to help administrators provide adequate support, resources, and professional development opportunities to English language teachers facing these challenges in public elementary schools. English Educators. The information collected in this research would heighten teachers' awareness in elementary and higher education institutions concerning the universal chal-

lenges English language teachers face, enabling curriculum development that would better equip aspiring teachers to navigate ESL classroom complexities. Parents. The study's findings would resonate with parents as they better understand the challenges faced by their children's English language teachers. This insight could foster more effective parent-teacher communication and collaboration, enabling parents to provide targeted support to their children's language learning journey. Future Researchers. This study would be a foundational resource for future researchers interested in exploring challenges within ESL classrooms in public elementary schools. The insights generated by this study could guide the formulation of research questions, methodologies, and analytical frameworks, enabling more comprehensive investigations into this area. The following terms or words were defined in this study to understand further the phenomenon under investigation: Elementary English Language Teachers. Education providers who primarily teach English subject areas from Grades 1 to 6. (Philippine K to 12 Curriculum) Pedagogical Frontiers. Innovative and evolving boundaries in educational methodologies, practices, and approaches.

1.4. Review of Related Literature—This chapter surveys pertinent literature and research relevant to the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of English language teachers in public elementary schools.

1.4.1. Experiences of English Language Teachers—Murray and Christison (2019) emphasize the importance of considering the identity and context of specific pedagogies in English language instruction, advocating for valuing students' self-identification to enhance learning. Derakhshan et al. (2020) note that in Iran, public school students often lack adequate English proficiency, leading many to enroll in private programs. They stress the importance of teachers having a positive attitude toward learners and the teaching process. Sultana

(2019) highlights the lack of assessment literacy among teachers in Bangladesh, particularly in rural schools, which raises concerns about teacher proficiency in language assessment.

Basil Khloud (2020) discusses the challenges faced by female secondary English teachers in Jordan, including academic difficulties and barriers related to student and community relations, teacher competencies, curriculum, and school infrastructure. Songbatumis (2018) identifies challenges for primary school English teachers in Indonesia, such as students' lack of vocabulary and motivation, insufficient teacher training, and inadequate resources. Rosa (2018) outlines strategies employed by teachers in Indonesia to address challenges like student respect, effective speaking instruction, and managing disruptive behavior.

Nijat (2019) examines psychological barriers to spoken English among Malaysian primary school pupils, recommending engaging activities and a supportive learning atmosphere to overcome these issues. Omar (2020) finds that interactive language learning activities improve students' willingness to engage in spoken communication in Malaysia. Listyariyani (2018) reveals that Indonesian teachers face challenges with pronunciation, access to resources, and diverse learning activities, suggesting the need for government support.

Halik and Nusrath (2020) identify challenges for English teachers in rural Sri Lanka, including students' disinterest, inadequate parental support, and poor learning environments. Fathi Derakhshan (2019) focus on the mental health of Iranian teachers, highlighting the importance of self-efficacy and emotional regulation in reducing teaching stress. Abdulwahab et al. (2022) report that English elementary teachers in rural areas face low salaries and inadequate resources, impacting their morale and student performance.

Dela Peña Musico (2024) emphasize the need for consistent instructional supervision

to improve teaching quality in Davao City. Domingo (2020) discusses the challenges of English language instruction in the Philippines, noting teachers' coping strategies and the importance of professional development. Espino et al. (2021) advocate for acknowledging different English language varieties in the curriculum.

Talidong Liu (2020) highlights the impact of technological advancements on English classrooms in General Santos City, recommending collaboration between educators and administrators.

1.4.2. Coping Mechanisms of English Language Teachers—Karabuğa Ilin (2019) state that ESL instructors commonly use a learner-centered approach, facilitating inductive learning. Mohamad et al. (2021) recommend leveraging technology and fostering supportive online learning environments to address challenges during the pandemic in Malaysia. Kohnke Jarvis (2021) identify innovative teaching practices and collaborative learning as key strategies for adapting to remote teaching in Hong Kong.

Haufiku et al. (2023) find that Namibian ESL teachers rely on motivating students, adopting learner-centered approaches, and utilizing diverse teaching materials. Gregersen et al. (2020) note that online language teachers in Sydney use active coping strategies like engaging activities and seeking emotional support. Aljaradeh (2020) shows that digital storytelling effectively enhances English learning among young learners in Jordan.

Imran et al. (2024) report that despite challenges, teachers in Punjab, Pakistan, employ innovative strategies to enhance English learning. Lagria (2021) suggests that professional development and peer mentoring programs are crucial for helping novice teachers in the Philippines. Canada et al. (2022) recommend maintaining a positive attitude and using practical examples to cope with teaching challenges in Pagadian City.

Alayon et al. (2023) highlight the impor-

tance of tailored support for reading comprehension in Pagadian City. Maquidato (2021) discusses coping strategies for managing anxiety and enhancing language skills, while Mendoza (2019) reveals differences in coping mechanisms between public and private school teachers in Sulu, Mindanao. Nasir and Aziz (2020) emphasize the use of collaborative learning to enhance speaking and writing skills in Malaysian primary classrooms.

Shan and Aziz (2022) recommend comprehensive training and resource improvement for English language instructors in Malaysia. Ayalew et al. (2022) investigate stress and coping strategies among English teachers in Ethiopia, highlighting the need for professional development and supportive teaching environments.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored on the Ecological Systems Theory of Urie Bronfenbrenner (2007). This theory states that one interacts with diverse surroundings that impact one's actions to varying extents throughout a person's life. These surroundings include the microsystem, mesosystem, ecosystem, macrosystem, and chronosystem. Such environments influence our behavior differently (Evans, 2023). In the context of English teachers' challenges in elementary schools, this theory provided a framework for understanding the interplay between teachers, the environments they are situated in, and the people they are surrounded with. This could be their students and parents, faculty colleagues, the school and its administrators, the school policies and community resources, and the larger schemes and facets of the educational system. Furthermore, this theory was solidified by the self-determination theory developed by Edward L. Deci and Richard M. Ryan (1985) which was cited by Cherry, K. (2022). This theory advocates that if the needs of people for competence, connection, and autonomy are satisfied, they will become self-determined. Applying this theory in this research would explore how English teachers'

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

sense of autonomy in their curriculum, their perceived competence in handling diverse teaching situations, and their interactions with students, colleagues, and parents impact their overall job satisfaction, engagement, and willingness to overcome challenges. This theory would uncover factors contributing to teachers' intrinsic motivation and how they could be enhanced to improve their experiences and effectiveness. Ultimately, Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977) provided additional backing for the premise of this research. This theory elucidates how individuals assimilate new behaviors, attitudes, and emotional reactions by observing, imitating, and engaging with others in their social milieu. It underscores the significance of cognitive processes and the combined impact of external circumstances and internal factors on the development of human behavior (McLeod, 2023). This theory could be applied to English teachers in primary schools to understand how they acquire new teaching strategies, classroom management techniques, and coping mechanisms through observation, interaction with colleagues, and professional development activities. It could shed light on how teachers learn from each other's successes and challenges, leading to the diffusion of effective practices within the school community. Examining teachers' social interactions and networks could give insight into how these dynamics influence their experiences and ability to address

challenges. Numerous studies have explored the coping strategies employed by English teachers working in public elementary or primary schools across diverse geographical locations. These investigations have shed light on how educators from various parts of the world navigate the challenges inherent in their roles. Despite the contextual variations arising from distinct educational systems, cultural contexts, and linguistic environments, a notable consensus has emerged. These teachers encountered shared difficulties that cut across boundaries, indicating a need for collective attention. While their specific challenges might differ, recognizing these hurdles emphasized the importance of developing practical, inclusive, targeted support mechanisms to address these universal issues. The conceptual framework for understanding English teachers' challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights in public elementary schools was built upon synthesizing several vital theoretical perspectives mentioned above. This framework aimed to understand how these teachers steer their professional roles within the unique context of English education in public elementary schools. Finally, the challenges include a lack of resources and access to educational materials for teachers and students, the digital divide, consideration of school facilities and equipment, difficulty developing proficiency, skills, and behavior of learners, and problems with insufficient knowledge and technical skills.

2. Methodology

This chapter successfully met the study's objectives by detailing the systematic approaches and methods employed in phenomenological research. It also described the chosen research design and my responsibilities as the researcher during the study's execution. It provided comprehensive insights into the research subjects, explaining the procedures and selection criteria I utilized. The chapter concluded by examining the techniques I used for data collection and analysis and the strategies implemented in maintaining ethical standards throughout my research.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions of the Study—The philosophical and qualitative assumptions of a study were crucial in guiding the research process of my study. Four core assumptions underpinned my qualitative research's understanding, encompassing ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological assumptions. These foundational assumptions shaped my research design and influenced my approach as a qualitative researcher. According to Zukauskas et al. (2018), a paradigm is a comprehensive framework or viewpoint that directs and influences how researchers approach their studies, develop research questions, collect data, analyze results, and interpret findings. It includes a collection of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical foundations that shape researchers' conceptualization and execution of their research. In this study, the paradigm informed the selection of my methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the entire research process and ensuring coherence throughout my study. **Ontology.** According to Grass (2024), ontology in research refers to the underlying beliefs about the nature of reality and what can be known about it. It addresses whether researchers view the empirical world as objective and independent of human perception (positivist stance) or as constructed and influenced by social and cultural contexts (constructivist). In this research study, the ontology guided my approach to gathering and interpreting data. For instance, I recognized that my participants have different experiences, realities, and understandings of a particular phenomenon—in this sense, their experiences as English teachers in public elementary schools. Hence, the ontological principle guided me to use interviews and thematic analysis to capture the richness and complexity of their perspectives. **Epistemology.** According to Grass (2024), the concept of epistemology is applied in qualitative research by seeking objective knowledge. This means findings should be based on evidence, not influenced by personal biases, and can be tested and reproduced by others. This can be attained by using logical methods to assess evidence objectively. Simply put, I established this principle by noting that my research participants' views are separate from mine and that their responses could be validated and reproduced in future studies related to my research. Hence, I used Colaizzi's data analysis method to analyze the data drawn from my research participants objectively and ensured that I did not impose nor imply anything outside of the raw data of my research study. **Methodology.** According to Grass (2024), methodology in research refers to the specific methods and strategies used to collect and analyze data to achieve scientific goals. It guides how a study is conducted through case studies, surveys, experiments, or other methods. In relation to my study, the concept of methodology was applied when I specifically utilized a phenomenological research design that fits my study. Since I wanted to explore the English teachers' experiences in public elementary schools by finding patterns and themes that they corroborated, such a design was most suitable. Hence, the method-

ological concept was applied. Axiology. In research, axiology refers to the study of values and how they influence the development and application of knowledge. It examines the appropriateness, goodness, or badness of knowledge. It addresses ethical and aesthetic issues, determining what is considered valuable or important in human behavior and the environment (Rosida et al., 2023). I applied the concept of axiology by constantly revisiting the ethical considerations stipulated in this study, thereby sternly following them to make my study ethical and fair. Rhetoric. In research, rhetoric involves the adept and persuasive use of language, communication techniques, and presentation methods to convey ideas, arguments, and findings, ultimately influencing the audience's understanding and perspective on the study (Beqiri, 2018). In my study, I employed the narration of the research responses in an engaging and respectful narrative style to honor my research participants' voices while effectively highlighting the importance of the findings. This approach enhanced the readability of my research and ensured that the interpretations were robust and rooted in the participants' experiences.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Employing a phenomenological research approach, I delved into the experiences of English teachers, focusing mainly on the obstacles they face in public elementary schools and their coping strategies. I aimed to collect comprehensive information about their experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms concerning the phenomenon under study. With phenomenology guiding my qualitative framework, I revealed the essence and significance of these educators' roles, emphasizing their distinct perspectives and the aspects of their experiences. As the qualitative researcher in this study, I aimed for an in-depth investigation that transcends superficial observations. My research centered on understanding the participants' experiences, challenges, and coping strategies related to the phenomenon. I

highlighted the importance of grasping the complexities of human experiences, considering the diverse perspectives shaped by unique contexts, backgrounds, and personal histories (Neubauer et al., 2019). To fully capture the complexity of teaching English in public elementary schools, my study focused on conducting in-depth interviews, engaging in reflective dialogues, and analyzing participants' narratives. I aimed to provide a detailed and contextually rich understanding of the challenges, successes, coping strategies, and insights related to teaching English in public elementary schools while adhering to phenomenological principles.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—It was crucial to determine what approach a researcher should employ in a study to tailor the most suitable design, data collection methods, and data analysis tool in a study. Hence, I used a qualitative research design in my research investigation. According to Busetto (2020), qualitative research aims to grasp the essence and specifics of phenomena, such as their characteristics, appearances, and the situations in which they arise. It examines subjects from various perspectives, not emphasizing quantifying their frequency or establishing causal relationships. Rather than relying on numerical data, qualitative research typically involves collecting and analyzing information expressed in words. The qualitative design was the most appropriate since I studied the lived experiences, coping strategies, and insights of English teachers teaching English in public elementary schools. I described and elaborated on this phenomenon rather than establishing or refuting theories. There are, however, specialized methods used in qualitative research, including grounded theory, narrative, case studies, phenomenology, and ethnography. In my study, I used phenomenological research design. According to Gagura (2024), phenomenological research is a qualitative approach centered on comprehending individuals' experiences in particular contexts. It employs interviews, ob-

servations, and personal reflections to explore the significance and essence of these experiences. This method emphasizes the importance of language and interpretation in understanding human experiences. The phenomenological research design was most suitable since I wanted to explore the personal experiences of English teachers as public teachers in elementary schools using in-depth interviews and since they were the most fit individuals who could testify their experiences concerning this context.

2.4. Research Participants—Creswell and Creswell (2018) pointed out that the number of participants in phenomenological research was 3 to 10. Thus, the participants in this study consisted of 10 English teachers from different public elementary schools under Tugbok A District, Division of Davao City. These schools were Tacunan Elementary School, Matina Biao Elementary School, Ula Elementary School, Tugbok Central Elementary School SPED Center, and Mintal Elementary School. 5 of the participants participated in the In-Depth Interview, and another 5 participants participated in the Focus Group Discussion. Additionally, these research participants were chosen through purposive sampling. According to Bisht, (2024), purposive sampling is a non-randomized sampling technique that chooses participants pertaining to specific criteria. Since my research study was all about English teachers' experiences as public elementary school teachers, I have hand-picked research participants who are best suited to give me genuine and real-time experiences under the phenomenon being studied. These participants were also selected based on the following criteria: they must be in teaching service for at least three years, be English teachers, and teach in public elementary schools mentioned above. Research participants were individuals who volunteered to take part in research studies. They were observed by researchers to collect data.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were crucial because they relate to the moral principles and guidelines that governed my conduct as a researcher. These principles ensured that I carried out my investigations responsibly, treating participants respectfully and striving to generate reliable and precise information. To protect my research participants, maintain scientific integrity, and foster trust within the research community, I adhered to the following established ethical standards in my research practices (Resnik, 2020). Social value. This concerns the potential benefits and favorable outcomes that research can bring to society, like addressing problems or improving people's quality of life. I evaluated the societal value of my study by acknowledging its potential impact and importance for the larger community. This ensures that resources are directed toward research that has the potential to create significant advantages for society. Informed Consent. This entails securing a participant's consent to join a research investigation after receiving comprehensive details about the study's objectives, procedures, possible disadvantages, and advantages. As the researcher in this study with teachers, it was incumbent upon me to guarantee that participants comprehended the study thoroughly and were entitled to it. This clarity enabled them to decide on participation with awareness, upholding their autonomy and dignity, and ensuring adherence to parental consent protocols. Vulnerability. The vulnerability of research participants pertains to their increased risk of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion due to factors such as age, cognitive ability, or socio-economic status. As a researcher, I needed to acknowledge and consider the potential vulnerability of these participants and take appropriate measures to protect them. This involved providing additional safeguards and support, such as obtaining informed consent from the participants, ensuring confidentiality, and carefully explaining their rights and the study's

procedures in a way they could understand. Additionally, I modified research methods to minimize potential adverse effects, ensuring that the well-being of these participants was prioritized throughout the study. Risks, benefits, and safety. In research, it is essential to carefully evaluate the potential risks and benefits associated with participation in a study and implement measures that safeguard the well-being of participants. These elements involved assessing the potential disadvantages and advantages of participating in a study, along with establishing strategies to ensure the welfare of participants. In this investigation, as the researcher, I meticulously assessed and balanced these factors, ensuring that the potential benefits outweigh the risks. I put adequate precautions in place to minimize harm while optimizing participants' safety, particularly considering student participants' vulnerabilities. This comprehensive approach was crucial to maintaining ethical standards and protecting the participants throughout the research process. Privacy and confidentiality. Privacy and confidentiality in research are about safeguarding participants' personal information and ensuring their identity remains confidential unless they explicitly consent to disclosure. In the context of this study, I was responsible for implementing appropriate protocols to secure participants' data and maintain confidentiality. This included anonymizing data, securely storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. These measures were crucial to protect participants' privacy and uphold the research process's integrity. Justice. This concept relates to the equitable allocation of the advantages and disadvantages resulting from research across various segments of society. In this study, I ensured that my research was inclusive, avoiding exploiting or excluding vulnerable groups. Additionally, I strived to make the research's benefits accessible to all who could benefit from them. This approach promoted fairness and equity throughout the re-

search process, ensuring that no group bore an undue burden or was left out of the potential gains from the findings. Transparency. Transparency in research encompasses maintaining integrity at every phase of the study, from its conception and execution to reporting results. In this study, I offered clear and truthful information regarding my research methodologies and outcomes. Furthermore, I was receptive to examination and feedback. Transparency acted as a catalyst for trust, credibility, and accountability within the research community and the general public. This commitment to openness ensured that the process and results of my research were accessible and understandable to all stakeholders involved. The qualification of a researcher. The qualification of a researcher relates to one's academic background, professional experience, and proficiency in a particular area of study, ensuring that one possesses the requisite abilities and knowledge to conduct the research competently. In this investigation, I held suitable qualifications that showcase my capability to conduct research, analyze data, and interpret the results. My expertise and training provided the foundation to approach this study with a rigorous scientific method and critical analytical skills, ensuring the integrity and validity of the findings. The adequacy of facilities. This addresses the presence and suitability of the essential resources, tools, and infrastructure required to execute a study efficiently and securely. In this research, I guaranteed access to appropriate investigation facilities. This opportunity enabled the development of reliable and uniform findings while minimizing possible risks to the study participants. The presence of appropriate facilities ensured that both data gathering and analysis were carried out under conditions that maintained the utmost standards of research ethics and security. Community involvement. This encompasses the involvement and active engagement of community members, stakeholders, or the intended study population

throughout the research journey, from initial planning to sharing research outcomes. In this study, I engaged the community to guarantee the study's relevance, acceptability, and potential impact. Additionally, this involvement fostered trust and cooperation between me and the community. Engaging with the community not only helped to tailor the research to be more effective and meaningful but also enhanced the overall quality and applicability of the results. Plagiarism and fabrication. Researchers should strictly follow principles of academic honesty and integrity. This entails giving proper credit to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and verifying the accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employed tools like plagiarism detectors. I maintained thorough documentation of my research procedures to ensure that my work was devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries were authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhanced the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I ensured the research process was conducted fairly, objectively, and without personal bias, prejudice, or influence from outside sources. I created an environment that encouraged the open and honest exploration of ideas and promoted fairness in data collection and analysis. This commitment to impartiality helped to uphold the integrity of the research process and ensured that the findings were reliable, and representative of the true phenomena being studied. As an expert in qualitative methods, I was familiar with various qualitative research techniques, such as interviews, focus groups, and participant observation. I possessed the skills and knowledge to design, conduct, and analyze qualitative studies, ensuring that the research question was satisfactorily addressed, and the results were legitimate and dependable. My expertise in these methods allowed me to deeply explore complex social phe-

nomena and capture the nuanced experiences of participants, contributing to the validity and reliability of the research findings. As a data collector and keeper, I gathered information from various sources, such as interviews or observations, and ensured accurate and secure storage. I followed ethical guidelines, safeguarded participants' privacy, and ensured data was structured and available for later examination and understanding. This careful management of data helped maintain the integrity of the research process. It supported the production of credible, reliable findings that could be reviewed and utilized by others in the academic community. As a data analyst, I analyzed the gathered data to discover trends, patterns, and valuable perspectives following the research query. I utilized meticulous qualitative data analysis methods like coding and thematic analysis to extract significant findings and enrich the knowledge base within my discipline. This approach allowed me to deeply understand the data, providing insights that were relevant and contributed significantly to the field, enhancing scholarly discussions and practical applications related to the study topic. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, I was tasked with synthesizing and communicating the research findings concisely and coherently. This entails skillfully conveying the study's objectives, approaches, outcomes, and ramifications through written documents, presentations, or alternative means of transmitting information. I ensured the research results were easily accessible and comprehensible to the designated audience. This approach helped to maximize the impact of the findings, ensuring they are not only shared but also understood and utilized by others in ways that could further knowledge and influence practice in the field.

2.7. Data Collection—This study employed a systematic procedure to gather data. Several steps were taken to adhere to the proper data collection procedure, which ensured the data collection's accuracy and objectivity. The

following is the step-by-step process of gathering the needed data. Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School. To initiate the data collection process, I secured endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges. This process involved submitting formal letters outlining the research objectives and methodology, accompanied by any supporting documents. This crucial step occurred within the last two weeks of January 2024. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent and Public Schools District Supervisor. Upon receiving the endorsement, I requested permission from the school's division superintendent. This required submitting a formal letter detailing the research proposal's significance to the educational community. Along with the letter, I attached Chapters 1 and 2 of my thesis and the research instrument, clearly explaining the study's objectives and participant identification process. Moreover, before proceeding with the data collection, I waited for the response from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) and Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS). This step was undertaken from the last week of January 2024 until the last week of February 2024, ensuring that all necessary approvals were in place to conduct the research ethically and effectively. Asking for permission from the school heads. Once permission was granted, I sought approval from the school heads of the selected institutions. This step involves submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collection time frame. I asked permission to conduct the study from last week of February 2024 to last week of March 2024. Obtaining consent from the participants. With the school heads' approval, I asked for consent from the research participants through informed consent forms. These forms clearly explained the research purpose, participant rights, and confidentiality measures. This consent process ensured the participants were

fully informed and agreed to participate. Furthermore, consent from the participants was obtained from the last week of February 2024 until the last week of March 2024. Conducting the interview. Upon securing consent from all participants, I scheduled and conducted the interviews using a structured or semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The interviews took place in the last week of February until the last week of March 2024. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. Following the interview sessions, I meticulously transcribed the interviewees' remarks, carefully considering non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details. This procedure would use audio recordings and field notes to capture the breadth of participants' reactions comprehensively. The transcription of interviewee responses was scheduled for the first week of April 2024.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—After collecting the data, I began data coding and thematic content analysis. This involved methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories, sub-categories, and themes from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I formulated conclusions and gleaned insights directly related to the research objectives. This process allowed me to interpret the data effectively, ensuring that the findings accurately reflect the experiences and perspectives of the participants. I employed Colaizzi's method of data analysis in this study. Since the study covers different perspectives and portrayals of participants' responses concerning being English teachers in public elementary schools, such a method effectively explores the research participants' responses clearly and logically. According to Wirihana (2018), Colaizzi's approach to data analysis is rigorous and robust, making it a qualitative method that guarantees the trustworthiness and dependability of its outcomes. It enables researchers to uncover emerging themes and their intricate re-

relationships. The methodology involved multiple readings of each transcript to grasp its content comprehensively. Significant statements about the phenomenon were identified and extracted from each transcript, meticulously documented on separate sheets with corresponding page and line references. Meanings were derived from these statements and categorized into groups, clusters of themes, and overarching themes. The study's findings were synthesized into a detailed depiction of the phenomenon, elucidating its essential structure. Finally, validation was sought from the research participants to confirm that the descriptive findings accurately mirrored their experiences.

2.9. Trustworthiness of the Study—It is about how reliable, sensible, and authentic the research results are, ensuring that the conclusions are trustworthy and accurate. Then, Alexander, A. (2019) cited Lincoln and Guba's ideas regarding the trustworthiness of a research study. It was mentioned that trustworthiness refers to the evaluation of the quality and value of the complete study, while helping to find out how closely study findings reflect the objectives of the study based on the data supplied by the participants. Moreover, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often used to evaluate how reliable the study is. Credibility. Building credibility entails proving that the results are accurate. Credibility is important for this study because it evaluates whether the results accurately represent the realities and experiences of English teachers teaching in public elementary schools. I conversed with the participants for a long time to gain a thorough understanding of their experiences and increase my credibility. I also used triangulation, gathering information from various sources, including observations, interviews, and questionnaires. To confirm the interpretations, I gave the participants a preliminary version of the findings as part of member checking. Transferability. This refers to the degree to which the

results of this study can be used in different situations or with different populations, which is referred to as transferability. While the particular insights are closely linked to English teachers in a specific educational environment, I thoroughly explained the research context and methodology. The study's transferability was increased because this thorough, rich narrative enabled others, including educators, school administrators, and researchers, to assess how well the results apply to comparable contexts or populations. Confirmability. Confirmability deals with the study's objectivity by ensuring that the respondents, not my prejudices or biases, shaped the findings. To ensure confirmability, I kept a thorough audit trail detailing every step of the research process, from data collection to data analysis decisions. This methodological transparency made it possible for other researchers to evaluate the research's objectivity by following the study's development and reviewing the choices made. Dependability proves that the study results are reliable and repeatable in similar situations. This study's dependability was attained through meticulous documentation of the entire research procedure, including the data collection and analysis methods. Such documentation validates the research by ensuring that other researchers could duplicate the study and possibly produce consistent results. By following these standards, the research offered valid and trustworthy conclusions regarding the effects of teaching English in a public elementary school and a framework that researchers and other educators could use to compare similar learning environments. This methodology enhanced the study's standing in the academic community and provided insightful information for upcoming studies and instructional design.

2.10. Analytical Framework—The analytical framework in phenomenological research is a methodical and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I used Colaizzi's method to an-

alyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their lived experiences of English teachers teaching in public elementary schools. According to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi's (1978) method features a distinctive seven-step process offering rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminated in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relied on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which could be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews are common, data could also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enabled researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore their intricate relationships (Wirihana et al., 2018).

Data Familiarization. By reading and rereading the transcripts several times, I fully understood the meanings conveyed by the participants and gained a global sense of the phenomenon being studied. This thorough review process is crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants' statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences.

Identifying Significant Statements. I carefully identified every statement in the narratives directly related to the phenomenon I was studying. To identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data—such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews—was conducted. This step was essential to ensuring that my analysis stays on topic and provides a strong basis for future thematic development.

Formulating Meanings. After carefully examining the important statements, I determined meanings pertinent to the phenomenon. Although Colaizzi admits that complete bracketing is impossible, I reflexively “bracketed” my presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced.

To guarantee that the analysis stays rooted in the participants' real experiences, this process entails putting aside my interpretations as much as is practical.

Clustering Themes. By grouping the identified meanings into themes shared by all accounts, I ensured a rigorous analysis that remained true to the participants' experiences. Throughout this process, presuppositions must be bracketed to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. By letting the themes naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces, the integrity of the analysis was preserved. Developing an exhaustive description. I incorporated every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the phenomenon that I wrote. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description seeks to convey the essence and complexity of the phenomenon. By taking this step, it is ensured that the final representation presents a comprehensive perspective of the experiences that each participant has had.

Producing the fundamental structure. I broke down the lengthy explanation into a succinct statement highlighting the key elements that I believe are crucial to understanding the phenomenon's structure. This succinct synthesis effectively and concisely communicated the essence of the participants' experiences, concentrating on the essential components necessary for comprehending the phenomenon. Seeking verification of the fundamental structure. I asked participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflects their experience by returning it to all participants or, in more extensive studies, to a subsample. I went back and changed the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings were increased, and the analysis was firmly based on the participants' perspectives. The following figure illustrates this rigorous process, highlighting each step to comprehensively

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study explain the actions taken to analyze the data.

3. Results and Discussion

This section of the research focuses on addressing specific research inquiries and collecting feedback from English language instructors working in public elementary schools. These educators generously provided their personal experiences, strategies for handling challenges, and valuable insights gained from their roles as English teachers within the Tugbok A District public elementary schools.

3.1. The Experiences of English Teachers In Public Elementary Schools—In today’s dynamic landscape of public education, English teachers grapple with many challenges in their classrooms. Among these obstacles, perhaps the most pervasive is the student’s lack of motivation and interest in the subject matter. In tandem with this issue, a growing number of students arrive in classrooms burdened by anxiety, which further hampers their ability to engage fully in the learning process. Another significant challenge lies in the limited availability of resources for diversifying English lessons, hindering the creation of engaging and interactive activities.

Lastly, there is an overarching concern about students’ poor comprehension and low literacy skills, as many struggle to communicate effectively in English. These multifaceted challenges demand innovative approaches and dedicated efforts to create a more conducive environment for English learning in our public schools.

3.1.1. Students’ lack of motivation and interest—In English education within public schools, teachers struggle to pique and sustain students’ interest in a subject that many find intimidating or boring. Several factors contribute to this problem, including many students entering these classrooms without enthusiasm for

English. They frequently perceive it as either too difficult or simply uninteresting. This lack of enthusiasm can be attributed to previous educational experiences, personal disinterest in the traditional pieces of literature taught, or a mismatch between the curriculum and the student's daily lives and interests.

The responses also deemed that teachers suffer from students due to their lack of interest and motivation in learning the English language. The reason varies, from students seeing the subject as a mere academic requirement to not seeing it as valuable. Also, students have differing backgrounds, interests, and experiences in learning the language; thus, it affects their perspective toward learning it. Most participants emphasized students' lack of motivation or interest in learning the English language. Based on their responses, students often view English as an academic burden rather than a practical skill. The participants discussed the reasons behind the disinterest. According to ET1 and ET5, the English language lacks practical relevance in the students' daily lives. In the study of Dilshad et al. (2019), students are demotivated to learn English due to several reasons. These reasons include a lack of confidence, problems in speaking English, and poor knowledge of grammar. Since it lacks practicality, some students lack the motivation and find the subject boring. This result aligns with Halik and Nusrath's (2020) study, which found that negative attitudes toward learning English, a lack of motivation and guidance, and disinterest in the language can stem from low-income backgrounds and limited foundational knowledge of English. On the other hand, participants ET4 and ET8 mentioned that students lose interest in learning the English language because of language barriers and its complexity. In the responses from the participants, ET4 talks about modifying their teaching strategy by using simpler English and incorporating translations to improve comprehension, an important tactic in multilingual con-

texts. Additionally, ET6 implies adapting or revising the curriculum to reflect the student's interests and cultural backgrounds better. According to Filgona et al (2020), the motivation of learners is essential in order for them to succeed in their academics. Motivation urges them to want to know, to act, to understand, to believe, or even to gain some practical knowledge, skills, attitudes, or values.

3.1.2. Low Literacy Skills among Students—Another significant challenge for English teachers in public schools is improving their students' low comprehension and literacy skills. Although some students master basic English fundamentals such as grammar and writing, many struggle with confidence and proficiency when communicating effectively due to poor comprehension.

These responses from English teachers highlight several key challenges in teaching English in public elementary schools, particularly emphasizing language comprehension, reading, and writing skills. One of the problems students have in their English classes concerns their literacy skills, specifically in reading and writing, and their poor comprehension. It is obvious from the participants' responses that most of their students face language comprehension issues. According to one of the participants, ET1 and ET5, many students struggle to understand the said language, which necessitates teachers translating the English words into their mother tongue. The lack of vocabulary mastery among students and translating the English language into their native language is a challenge for teachers because it defeats the purpose of teaching English. This result aligns with Songbatumis' (2017) as cited in the study of Akram et al. (2020) study, which stated that the student's lack of vocabulary mastery was one of the challenges that emerged during their investigation. Some participants (ET2, ET3, ET5, ET6) also shared that students struggle greatly with reading and writing in English,

and some cannot form sentences or understand what they read. This mirrors Nijat's 2019 study, which stated that some students are not confident enough to speak English due to fear and anxiety, which significantly affects their performance. Additionally, this finding is supported by Halik and Nusrath's (2020) study, which shows that a lower level of basic knowledge in English is one of the challenges teachers encounter. In a study by Rosa (2018), he looked at the difficulties elementary school teachers encountered when instructing second-grade students, mainly when teaching English in Sdi Al Muttaqin Driyorejo Gresik, Indonesia. Results have shown that effective speaking instruction, which affects students' speaking skills, is part of other problems they have in their English subjects. To solve this issue, participants ET1 and ET5 shared that English teachers often translate English into the students' mother tongue to ensure comprehension. Additionally, ET4 and ET5 also mentioned that to aid students' comprehension, teachers often read for students and use different actions and gestures to help students' understanding.

3.1.3. Scarcity of Diverse English Teaching Materials—For English teachers in public schools, the scarcity of resources presents a significant challenge in their quest to deliver diverse and engaging lessons that cater to their students' multifaceted needs. The limitations may encompass a dearth of up-to-date textbooks, supplementary materials, technological resources, or even access to authentic language experiences outside the classroom.

From the participants' responses, it can be inferred that teachers find it difficult to handle English classes due to a lack of updated textbooks, the digital divide, and writing material supplies. These answers shed light on the major resource-related difficulties that English teachers in public elementary schools encounter. The lack of teaching resources and support materials impacts the quality of instruction and stu-

dent's capacity to learn. According to participant ET1, since students do not use English at home, school is the primary setting for exposure to and learning the language, necessitating the provision of sufficient resources. The scarcity of resources, learning materials, and facilities are some of the challenges teachers face in teaching English to elementary students. This result is also under the findings of Listiyariyani's study in 2018 which revealed that teachers had limited access to the learning resources of their school and there are not enough diverse learning activities focused on English and language learning. Furthermore, according to teachers, participants ET1, ET3, and ET5 consistently reported a scarcity of essential teaching resources, such as books, workbooks, and other educational materials. This is echoed in the study by Halik and Nusrath (2020), which found that all participants faced challenges due to a shortage of teaching and learning materials in schools. Similarly, Rosa's (2018) study corroborates these findings by highlighting that teachers do not have enough time to craft their own teaching aids because of the limited time they have at hand. They work the whole day juggling their role as classroom managers, and teachers, and they are also doing administrative roles. Participant ET8 noted insufficient technological resources to enhance English language teaching and learning. This reflects similar issues highlighted in Saeed Al-Sobhi and Preece's (2018) study, which identified the lack of necessary facilities as a hindrance to the process of teaching English to students. Additionally, the study pointed to issues like insufficient class time allocation for subjects and principals' overpowering role. These issues are further confirmed by Songbatumis (2017), as cited in the study of Akram et al. (2020), who observed that a lack of resources and facilities impairs the effectiveness of English teachers in classrooms. Likewise, Moses and Mohamad's (2019) study found that teaching English, specifically writing,

Fig. 3. The Experiences of English Teachers in Public Elementary Schools has become challenging because of students’ books, and reading materials. difficulties, including the lack of exposure to

Figure 3 shows the experiences of English teachers in public elementary schools. Three themes emerge the scarcity of Diverse English Teaching Materials, Students’ Lack of Motivation and Interest, and Low Literacy among Students.

3.2. *The Coping Mechanisms of English Teachers in Public Elementary Schools*—Elementary English teachers employ a multifaceted approach to cope with the challenges of their classrooms, relying on teamwork and mutual support to exchange ideas and overcome obstacles collaboratively. Engaging in continuous professional development ensures they stay at the forefront of effective teaching methods, evolving with the educational landscape. To create a vibrant and effective learning atmosphere, these educators infuse language-focused activities into their lessons, fostering an environment where students acquire language skills and develop a love for English-related subject areas.

3.2.1. *Teacher’s Collaborative Support*—English teachers in elementary school usually depend on the strength of teamwork and assistance from their professional community. Collaborating with their co-teachers provides an invaluable chance to share teaching approaches,

resources, and ideas. Teachers can share effective strategies, tackle shared problems, and develop original solutions when they work as a team. Teachers can encourage one another to improve their English teaching methods in a supportive and cooperative environment that fosters camaraderie.

The participant responses gathered during the interviews highlight the significance of professional learning communities (PLCs) and mentorship in fostering the professional development of English teachers. In addition to improving teachers’ abilities and expertise, these collaborative engagement methods offer teachers emotional support and useful guidance for resolving difficult situations in the classroom. Based on the accounts from Participant ET1, teachers value the ongoing collaboration and learning opportunities offered by Professional Learning Communities (PLCs), as these interactions help them refine their teaching methods and address challenges. Additionally, ET2 and ET8 emphasize that formal or informal mentorship from more experienced teachers is essential for providing guidance, encouragement, and managing stress. This finding corroborates the results of the study conducted by Lagria

(2021), in which they observed that English language teachers actively seek assistance from co-teachers as a practical solution to manage working in public school settings. Moreover, the feedback from ET4 and ET5 underscores the importance of engaging with colleagues for mutual support and sharing best practices, significantly enhancing professional development and problem-solving capabilities. According to Haufiku et al. (2023), collaborative teaching methods, including teachers' teamwork, have been identified as an effective means of addressing challenges in English classrooms. Collaborating with teachers through professional learning communities, sharing sentiments, and asking for assistance greatly provides teachers with different ways to tackle and face challenges, giving them more choices to transform their teaching practices effectively.

3.2.2. Professional Development—Continuous growth is at the heart of effective teaching, and elementary English educators frequently engage in ongoing professional development to stay abreast of the latest pedagogical trends and methodologies. Workshops, conferences, and online courses offer valuable opportunities for teachers to refine their skills, explore new teaching techniques, and gain fresh perspectives on language instruction. By investing in their professional development, elementary English teachers equip themselves with the tools necessary to adapt to evolving educational landscapes and provide a richer and more engaging learning experience for their students.

The responses above from English teachers underscore the significance of continuous professional growth, achieved through self-directed learning initiatives and official training supplied by educational authorities. Each strategy shows a dedication to improving and modifying instruction to meet the needs of students learning English successfully. According to the participants (ET3, ET7, ET8, ET9), to stay up to date with new teaching techniques and educa-

tional trends, many educators value organized training opportunities like seminars and workshops provided by the Department of Education. Seminars allow teachers to spend time with educators with the same mindset as them, helping each other to widen their knowledge and skills in English language teaching. Teaching is a life-long process; thus, attending avenues such as this provides them with more knowledge to become more effective in the classroom. Canada et al. (2022) further solidify this coping strategy as they believe that engagement in seminars and workshops helps teachers attain lesson objectives and quality education in English classrooms. Lagria's study (2021) in Eastern Samar also found that teachers become more competent through training, self-learning, skills enhancement, and professional development. Additionally, much emphasis is placed on the independence of continuing one's education via self-directed means like reading, taking online classes, and using a variety of learning resources as stipulated in the response of ET10. The result of this study corroborates the assertion made by Shan and Aziz (2022) that pragmatic solutions encompass providing comprehensive training for English language instructors and fostering positive perspectives. Formal seminars, trainings, and workshops provide teachers with critical new skills and techniques for effectively teaching a diverse student population. Additionally, self-directed learning enables teachers to customize their professional development to meet their unique needs and teaching styles, increasing their engagement and effectiveness. As highlighted by the teachers committed to continuous self-improvement, lifelong learning is crucial for personal and professional growth.

3.2.3. Language-focused activities—Creating a vibrant language-learning environment involves incorporating a diverse range of activities that cater to different learning styles. Elementary English teachers often employ language-focused activities that en-

hance language skills and make learning enjoyable. These activities may include interactive games, storytelling sessions, and language-based projects that encourage students to participate actively in the learning process. By infusing creativity and variety into their lesson plans, teachers can capture the attention of young learners and instill a love for language that extends beyond the classroom.

The responses from English teachers show many tactics used to improve English language instruction in public elementary schools. These strategies include technology, hands-on learning, differentiated teaching, and parental participation. Language-focused activities are crucial in creating a sense of fun and interest in English classes from the student's perspective. For English teachers, integrating contextualization and real-life activities while incorporating technology to emphasize language is an effective strategy for helping learners grasp lessons more effectively. Nasir and Aziz (2020) support these claims, asserting that language-focused activities, coupled with differentiated instruction tailored to individual students, aid English teachers in overcoming significant challenges. Participants ET1 and ET2 reported integrating language learning apps and digital resources to improve vocabulary and grammar skills. This result is aligned with the study of Canada et al. (2022), in which they discovered that some of the coping strategies of the teachers include being flexible and facilitative in teaching English and leveraging technology to improve teaching and learning. Meanwhile, additional participants such as ET8, ET6, and ET7 indicated that their main approach centers on tailoring their teaching methods to meet the varied learning

requirements of their students. Omar (2020) adds to this viewpoint by exploring students' views on interactive language learning activities to enhance English speaking skills in Malaysia. His study sought to evaluate the impact of these activities on students' motivation to participate in oral communication during language classes. The results indicated that interactive language learning successfully tackled communication obstacles within the classroom setting. Other participants (ET1, ET2, and ET8) also mentioned addressing challenges by involving students in practical, interactive activities that promote active learning. This approach aligns with the findings of Karabuğa and Ilin (2019), who emphasized a learner-centered approach in their ESL classes through inductive learning. Instead of explicitly teaching grammatical rules, teachers guided students to infer them through interactions with the second language. Digital learning apps such as Memrise and Hello Talk enhance the educational experience by making learning more interactive and engaging, potentially improving student interest and retention. Additionally, these technologies offer students opportunities for extra practice outside of traditional classroom settings. Implementing differentiated teaching strategies ensures that the diverse academic needs of each student are met, fostering more effective learning. Personalized learning approaches can significantly enhance students' overall academic performance in English. Furthermore, incorporating hands-on activities deepens understanding and retention of language concepts and develops critical thinking and collaborative skills by actively involving students in their learning process.

Figure 4 shows the coping mechanisms of English teachers in public elementary schools and the emergence of three themes: professional development and language-focused activities.

3.3. *The Educational Insights of English Teachers In Public Elementary Schools*—Drawing from their experiences, public elementary English teachers have garnered crucial insights

Fig. 4. The Coping Mechanisms of English Teachers in Public Elementary Schools

to enrich their classrooms. They recognize the indispensable role of technology, seamlessly integrating it into their lessons to make English learning interactive and relevant. Simultaneously, they emphasize fostering strong relationships with students, creating an atmosphere of trust and support that enhances communication and active participation. These educators also prioritize contextualized learning, intertwining language lessons with real-life situations and cultural contexts, ensuring that English education is theoretical and immediately applicable. Finally, the acknowledgment of the diverse needs of their students underscores the importance of comprehensive support—academic, emotional, and social—to nurture a holistic learning environment that encourages resilience and contributes to overall student development.

3.3.1. Technology is Important in English Classrooms—In the ever-evolving landscape of education, elementary public English teachers recognize the pivotal role of technology in enhancing their classrooms. Whether through interactive whiteboards, educational software, or online resources, teachers leverage technology to create dynamic and engaging lessons. Integrating digital tools caters to diverse learning styles and prepares students for the technology-driven world while making learning English

more interactive and relevant.

The feedback from English teachers underscores the crucial role of technology in improving English teaching and learning in public elementary schools. They stress the need for adaptability, creativity, and the importance of integrating technological tools with students’ needs and evidence-based practices. Based on the participants’ narratives (ET4, ET6, ET9, ET10), teachers are incorporating technology into their teaching to make English classes more dynamic and engaging. English teachers believe in the power of technology and educational trends in English classrooms. However, resources are scarce. According to ET4, there is a need for teachers to be proactive in developing and utilizing technology. Songbatumis (2017) as cited in the study of Akram et al. (2020) highlights the obstacle of technological unfamiliarity as a significant challenge in English classrooms. In response, Canada et al. (2022) emphasize the crucial role of teachers in overcoming this challenge. They posit that educators should actively engage with and integrate technology into English classrooms, staying abreast of educational trends. This proactive approach not only addresses students’ evolving needs but also ensures the delivery of high-quality education. This further supports the response of partici-

pant ET6, who requires teachers to be adaptable and creative, particularly in using technology to meet diverse student needs. Technologies such as virtual workshops, collaborative tools, and immersive experiences have the potential to revolutionize traditional English classrooms, turning them into vibrant learning environments. Moreover, technology can ensure that students can access educational materials within and beyond the classroom, particularly valuable in areas with limited resources. Teachers can address these resource gaps by leveraging technology to create cost-effective educational materials and activities. For technology integration to be successful and impactful, teachers must embrace adaptability and creativity to align technological applications with their students' needs and benefits.

3.3.2. *Building Connections with Students is Essential*—Beyond the curriculum, elementary public English teachers understand the profound impact of fostering strong relationships with their students. Creating a supportive and trusting environment promotes effective communication and encourages students to participate in class actively. By establishing connections, teachers can better understand individual learning needs, tailor their approach accordingly, and inspire a sense of belonging that enhances the overall English learning experience.

The answers provided by English teachers show a strong dedication to comprehending and adjusting English instruction to meet the varied needs of students. To effectively support all learners, these educators stress the value of cultural sensitivity, personal connection, and adaptability in instructional methods. The English teachers' approaches emphasize the significance of cultivating strong relationships with students as the foundation for effective education. Through personalized connections and understanding of each student's unique qualities, they foster a positive and supportive English learning environment that extends beyond aca-

ademic progress, contributing to students' overall growth and well-being. Participants ET2 and ET6 emphasized the need for teachers to identify and adjust to each student's individual learning styles and needs. Other participants, such as ET4 and ET8, highlighted the significance of acknowledging students' cultural backgrounds and integrating multicultural aspects into their teaching. They suggested building connections with students to enhance their confidence, especially in language learning. These participants also advocated using direct interaction to evaluate and refine teaching approaches, ensuring they are tailored for optimal language acquisition. According to Semrow (2021), school is meant to be a safe environment for all students, and when students do not feel comfortable, their ability to learn and mental well-being can deteriorate. Thus, establishing good teacher-student connections enhances students' attendance, mental well-being, behaviors, and academic success. Kirk (2023) also solidifies this claim that strong teacher-student relationships will lead to higher students' academic achievement, good grades, and less destructive behaviors. It is critical to adapt teaching strategies to students' diverse learning styles by using techniques like differentiated instruction, which entails offering a variety of learning pathways so all students, regardless of ability, can succeed academically. While using various instructional technologies can help engage students in fresh and productive ways, flexible lesson planning allows for last-minute adjustments that meet students' needs. Furthermore, improving the effectiveness of instruction requires a thorough understanding of the cultural and familial backgrounds of the students. Teachers can create a more engaging and supportive learning environment that values and represents the diversity of their students by making lessons more inclusive and relatable.

3.3.3. *Contextualized Learning*—Recognizing the importance of relevance in educa-

tion, elementary public English teachers prioritize contextualized learning experiences. They strive to connect language lessons to real-life situations, cultural contexts, and students' interests. Through literature, discussions, and activities grounded in the students' experiences, teachers ensure that language acquisition is not just a theoretical exercise but a practical skill with immediate applicability in their lives. Gleaned from the English teachers' responses, the key to capturing students' interest and promoting a profound grasp of the language is the integration of real-life relevance into English lessons. The instructor underscores the transformative impact of contextualized learning, emphasizing its ability to make lessons engaging, highlight practical language applications, and foster a deeper understanding of linguistic nuances through real-world examples and current events. This approach enhances language skills and instills a sense of purpose and appreciation for effective communication in diverse contexts. Participant ET2 highlighted the importance of adaptability in teaching, emphasizing the need for educators to modify their teaching methods in response to the evolving dynamics of the classroom and the shifting needs of students. It is also crucial to contextualize lessons, making them relatable and easily understandable for students, enhancing their engagement and comprehension. According to Osika et al. (2023), integrating context enriches students' learning encounters and results. Students gain a deeper comprehension when learning is aligned with real-world scenarios, particularly in a workplace setting. They are more adept at applying and transferring their knowledge beyond traditional classroom boundaries. Including contextualization introduces an additional dimension to the learning process, fostering interest, curiosity, motivation, and engagement with the subject matter. More so, contextualization helps

improve students' reading and comprehension skills and levels as part of English language domains (Sambayon et al., 2023).

3.3.4. Support is Needed—Acknowledging the diverse needs of their students, elementary public English teachers emphasize the significance of providing adequate support. This support extends beyond academic assistance to include emotional and social well-being. Teachers recognize that a supportive environment encourages risk-taking, fosters resilience, and enhances learning outcomes. Whether through differentiated instruction or additional resources, the commitment to offering comprehensive support reflects the dedication of elementary public English teachers to the holistic development of their students.

Ultimately, English teachers believe that prioritizing students' diverse needs is paramount for their success in learning English. By offering additional support such as differentiated instruction, extra resources, and personalized feedback, the instructor ensures that students can progress at their own pace and effectively overcome challenges. Emphasizing creating a supportive learning environment, the approach acknowledges varying learning styles, utilizing tools like tutoring, peer collaboration, and tailored materials to foster an inclusive space where every student can thrive academically. As indicated by Hassan et al. (2023), the perception of social support plays a crucial role in empowering students to enhance their self-esteem and cultivate a positive social network that helps in meeting basic needs, ultimately contributing to improved success outcomes. Additionally, Wei (2022) emphasizes recognizing students' presence both within the learning environment and in various facets of life as a means through which teachers can actively contribute to their students' mental well-being.

Fig. 5. The Educational Insights Gained by English Teachers in Public Elementary Schools.

Figure 5 shows the educational insights of English Teachers in Public Elementary Schools and the four themes emerging. Technology was important in English classrooms; contextualized learning and support are needed to foster it.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, I present a summary of the study. I derived implications and future directions from the findings summarized here. My research aimed to investigate the experiences, coping strategies, and insights of English teachers teaching in public elementary schools in Tugbok A District, Division of Davao City. To achieve my research objectives, I employed a qualitative phenomenological research design. I utilized thematic analysis for data analysis, following the approach outlined by Colaizzi (1978), as cited in the study of Wirihana, Welch, Williamson, Christensen, Bakon, and Craft (2018). In this study, I comprehensively describe the experiences shared by public elementary English teachers. These teachers possess valuable knowledge about the phenomenon under investigation, which was thoroughly discussed in the previous chapter.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the experiences of English teachers in public elementary schools were students’ lack of motivation and interest, low literacy skills, and lack of resources for English lessons variety. The English teachers’ coping mechanisms included collaborative support, professional development, and language-focused activities. Lastly, the findings drawn from the study were that fostering relationships with students is deemed necessary, contextualized learning, and needs support for students.

4.2. Implications—Based on the findings of the study, the corresponding result revealed that The experiences of English teachers in public elementary schools. Three themes emerge: the scarcity of diverse English teaching materials, students’ lack of motivation and interest, and low literacy among students. These were common concerns and issues that were observed during the discussions. Students are demoti-

vated by the structure and allocation of rewards. Students do not perceive the classroom climate as supportive. Students have other priorities that compete for their time and attention. Students may suffer from physical, mental, or other personal problems affecting motivation. The coping mechanisms of English teachers in public elementary schools and the emergence of three themes: professional development and language-focused activities. Professional development or continuing education and career training after a person can positively help address the student's lack of interest. Somehow, teachers know how to handle the students' concerns about English teaching materials, lack of motivation and interest, and low literacy among students. The educational insights of English Teachers in Public Elementary Schools. The emerging of the four themes. The technology used was crucial in English classrooms; contextualized learning and support are needed to foster it. This study unveiled significant challenges English teachers face in public elementary schools, such as a lack of student motivation and interest, poor literacy skills, and insufficient resources. Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach involving collaboration between teachers, parents, and the Department of Education.

4.3. *Future Directions*—Teachers and parents may work together to enhance student motivation and literacy skills. Parents should actively support their children's learning at home, especially in reading and spelling, while teachers should provide patient and constructive feedback. Teachers should correct errors kindly rather than reacting negatively to mistakes, fostering a supportive environment that builds students' confidence. Teachers may employ contextualized teaching methods and incorporate interactive and engaging activities like group work and multimedia resources to make lessons more relatable and meaningful. Differentiated instruction is essential to cater to student's diverse

needs and capabilities. Implementing extracurricular activities, language clubs, or events that create a language-rich environment can give students additional opportunities to practice speaking skills in a more relaxed setting, boosting their confidence and communication abilities. The Department of Education may consider implementing a comprehensive support program to support these classroom practices. This program may include professional development workshops and training sessions for English teachers, focusing on strategies to boost student motivation and interest in language learning. Establishing a mentorship program within schools, where experienced teachers share effective strategies with their peers, could further enhance teaching practices. Another significant challenge was the lack of resources for English lessons. The Department of Education should advocate for increased funding and resource allocation for English language programs in public schools. Establishing partnerships with publishers, educational technology companies, and community organizations can provide supplementary materials, online resources, and other aids to enrich English lessons. Reducing class sizes could also help teachers monitor and support their students more effectively. This study also highlights the importance of professional development for teachers. Encouraging teachers to pursue further training, seminars, and workshops could help them adopt new coping strategies to address their challenges. The Department of Education should allocate funds for technological resources and urge schools to utilize computer and speech laboratories for the benefit of their students. Finally, fostering strong relationships between teachers and students was vital. Teachers should treat their profession as noble, providing a supportive and inspiring learning environment that encourages students to develop literacy and communication skills. Implementing these measures could significantly improve the overall effectiveness and

engagement of English lessons in public elementary schools. As I reflect upon the findings of my qualitative phenomenological study on English teachers' experiences in public elementary schools within Tugbok A, District, Davao City, I recognize the potential for further exploration and understanding of this significant educational phenomenon. The insights gained from my research provide a solid foundation for future investigations that could enhance teaching practices, academic policies, and the overall learning environment. One avenue for future research may delve deeper into the specific pedagogical strategies employed by English teachers in public elementary schools. Understanding the nuances of their instructional methods, including integrating technology, differentiated instruction, and innovative approaches, could shed light on effective teaching practices that positively impact student learning outcomes. This means that quantitative, correlational studies can be conducted to explore further the effectiveness of the coping mechanisms used by English teachers in this study toward students' academic achievement. Additionally, investigating the role of mentorship and professional development programs in supporting English teachers within this context may provide valuable insights into avenues for continuous improvement. Exploring the intersectionality of factors influencing English teachers' experiences is another promising direction for future research. Investigating how socio-economic factors, cultural backgrounds, and regional disparities impact teaching experiences could contribute to developing targeted interventions and policies that address the unique challenges educators face in diverse contexts. Additionally, a comparative analysis across various districts or regions

could provide a deeper insight into regional differences and aid in formulating context-specific strategies to enhance the quality of English language education in public elementary schools. In line with the evolving landscape of education, future research could also examine the integration of digital literacy and online teaching tools in the English language curriculum. Investigating how teachers navigate the challenges and opportunities presented by technology in their classrooms could provide valuable insights for curriculum development and teacher training programs. Additionally, exploring the impact of global events, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, on English teachers' experiences and the adaptation of remote teaching strategies is an area ripe for exploration. Furthermore, a longitudinal study tracking the career trajectories of English teachers in public elementary schools could offer a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing their professional development, job satisfaction, and retention rates. By identifying critical junctures in teachers' careers and the factors contributing to their longevity in the profession, policymakers and educational institutions can design targeted strategies to attract and retain high-quality educators. In conclusion, exploring English teachers' experiences in public elementary schools within Tugbok A District, Davao City, was a steppingstone for future research endeavors. By focusing on pedagogical strategies, socio-economic influences, technology integration, global events, and longitudinal career trajectories, researchers can contribute to the ongoing dialogue surrounding improving English language education in public elementary schools, ultimately fostering a more robust and effective educational system.

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